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MEMORANDUM

FROM: [REDACTED]
TO: The Parliamentary Select Committee on Constitutional, Legal, and Parliamentary Affairs
SUBJECT: OPPOSITION TO THE PROMOTION OF PROPER HUMAN SEXUAL RIGHTS AND GHANAIAAN FAMILY VALUES BILL, 2021
DATE: September 21, 2021.

SUMMARY

This is a Memorandum in Opposition to the passage of the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill. My reasons for opposition are as follows:

1. The bill is an affront to civil liberties.
2. The bill lacks a scientific understanding of the diversity of human sexuality.
3. The bill is religiously motivated and is based on majority perspectives.
4. The bill imposes compulsory surgery for inter-sex people at birth and that will be harmful.
5. The myth that homosexuality is not part of our culture and is a Western import.
6. Criminalizing LGBTQ persons as a way of protecting family values is not tenable.

ANALYSIS

1. The bill criminalizes not just “gay sex,” but any kind of advocacy for LBTQIA+ rights as well as freedom of expression and association. This violates the very democratic tenets of our constitution and therefore the bill must not be passed into law.
2. The bill is based on a very unscientific understanding of same-sex intimacies as unnatural. However, homosexuality is pervasive in the animal kingdom of which humans are part of. For this reason, homosexuality is no more unnatural than heterosexuality. Human sexuality also exists on a spectrum ranging from heterosexuality and homosexuality at the extreme ends with bisexuality and heterosexual tendencies all featuring on this scale. Human sexuality cannot be unnatural. The bill also assumes that homosexuality is a mental illness and/or a lifestyle choice which can be “cured.” Unfortunately, this erroneous view is the legacy of Western psychiatry and medicine which has long since been discarded beginning in the 1950s. Since the 1970s, the WHO, China and many other advanced countries have long struck that error from the list of mental and psychiatric disorders. Finally, the bill reduces the intimacy and emotions of same-sex relations to anal sex and this tendency to hypersexualize the LBTQIA community while scape-goating them for venereal diseases is neither humane nor ethical. This scape-goating rather exacerbates than curbs STDs. For this reason a bill based on unscientific assumptions about the LBTQIA community must not be passed into law.
3. Even though the Bill does not explicitly appeal to religious morality, many of its sponsors including Mr. Moses Foh-Amoaning, Rev. Lawrence Tetteh and the leadership of the Muslim community and “Traditionalists” have stated religious reasons why the bill needs to

be passed. I believe that secular and sociological framings of law rather than an appeal to religion is more suitable for a secular state such as Ghana. Religious edicts disguised as law simply reinforces the tyranny of the majority over sexual minorities. The constitution must guide and dictate the laws we pass and not religious books or scriptures.

4. The bills attempts to impose compulsory surgery to change the sex of intersex children at birth. This will definitely cause long term psychological distress and suffering to such individuals who may not have the capacity to make decision about their gender and sexual identities. We need laws to re-affirm love, support and inclusivity for inter-sex people rather than causing them psychological and emotional distress.
5. The pervasive myth that same-sex intimacies are alien to our culture and therefore the need to pass this bill is not tenable. Anthropologists and historians have recorded several ethnographic references to same-sex intimacies in ritual and social life in precolonial and colonial Ghana and Africa. If culture is the totality of our lived experiences, then same-sex intimacies which is a biological fact could not be said to be alien to Ghana and/or Africa.¹
6. The claim that the bill is to promote proper family values simply betrays the bill sponsors' connections with right wing American and Russian organizations who have a rather narrow conceptualization of the ideal family – man, wife and children, forming a nuclear unit. Ironically, before Christianization we had compound families and this didn't cause any moral angst. Stripping the members of the LGBTQ community of their rights in favor of an ideologically and religious-inspired notion of a heterosexual nuclear family does not promote “proper” family values but rather an ideological agenda. What breaks up families is marital infidelity, particularly of heterosexual men and parental irresponsibility. Besides love between two consenting adults cannot destroy families.

CONCLUSION

Due to all the above reasons, I am opposed to the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill and I respectfully urge Parliament not to pass the Bill. Thank you.

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[REDACTED], Accra.

¹ See for example Mark Epprecht, *Heterosexual Africa? The History of an Idea from the Age of Exploration to the Age of AIDS* (Ohio University Press, 2008).